

The Role of Open Schooling in Community Efforts to Tackle the Silent Pandemic of Antimicrobial Resistance

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This case study reports on an open schooling initiative for enhancing students' interest in science and understandings of relevant careers in the context of a public health issue. Framed within the design-based research paradigm, this pilot study enacted an open-schooling Teaching-Learning Sequence around the socio-scientific issue of Antimicrobial Resistance according to which students engage in scientific practices and bidirectionally collaborate with different stakeholders in the wider community. The participants were 74 students (13-14 years old) attending an urban secondary school. Data were collected utilizing a questionnaire and interviews with the students before and after the intervention. The findings from the pilot study suggest that students' genuine engagement in scientific practices, using actual equipment and collaborating with experts in out-of-school settings, while also promoting and sharing knowledge within a group setting, stimulated their interest and contributed to an improved perception of science in practice and, consequently, science-related careers. The findings may inform the design of open-schooling teaching and learning activities and provide practical recommendations for curriculum design and classroom practices with the potential to enhance students' interest in science and relevant careers.

Keywords: interest, open schooling, Antimicrobial Resistance.

Introduction

Globally, over the last two decades, societies face complex societal issues such as public health threats and climate change implications, that urgently call for citizens to act toward achieving sustainability (UNESCO, 2020). Recent data published by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD] (2021), indicate that not only cognitive skills but also transversal skills and attitudes acquired through lifelong learning will help individuals to thrive in a post-truth era. Tackling these growing issues demands scientifically literate citizens who can engage in public discourse and evidence-based reasoning and take informed decisions for a better quality of life. This set of skills can be fostered in science learning by practicing scientific thinking (Hazelkorn et al., 2015). Nevertheless, students' declining interest in science remains an issue of concern worldwide which also has a domino effect on the percentage of STEM education graduates (26%) particularly in Europe (OECD, 2019). Previous work (Drymiotou et al., 2021a) has shown that opportunities for active engagement in scientific practices with experts, connections between STEM careers and curricular topics as well as transferring science concepts to a real-life personally relevant context may succeed in enhancing students' interest in science and in studying and pursuing STEM careers. Hence, an important mission of educational institutions is to provide such opportunities to students and nurture them into becoming responsible citizens.

In doing so, the present pilot study aims to investigate opportunities to enhance students' interest in science by promoting the mechanism of *Open Schooling*. Open schooling is conceptualised within the context of project MULTIPLIERS (<https://multipliers-project.org/>), as an educational perspective in which schools become open to society by bidirectionally collaborating with different stakeholders to (a) improve community well-being by raising awareness and co-creating solutions to both personal and socially relevant problems; (b) engage in inquiry processes, construction of knowledge, creative action and dissemination processes at a local and global level, and (c) enrich the curricula and pedagogical approaches in schools while promoting meaningful

learning and competence development (Constantinou & Papadouris, 2012). This conceptualisation derives from a systematic review of existing good practices (i.e., a set of EU Open Schooling Calls, 12 EU-funded projects, 9 initiatives in the partner countries, and 50 articles) and a needs analysis using focus group interviews with 45 stakeholders.

This theoretically and empirically rooted conceptualisation guided the formulation of the framework for developing and enacting an open-schooling Teaching-Learning Sequence (TLS) (Papadouris & Constantinou, 2016, 2017) as shown on Table 1. Hence, this study aims to investigate whether open-schooling educational actions can enhance students' interest in science and their understandings of science careers by responding to the following research question:

Do open schooling educational actions influence:

- (a) students' interest in science?
- (b) students' career awareness?

Methods and Context

This study embraced a case-study approach with a case being defined as a group of 74 students (13-14 years old, 42 identified as female and 32 identified as male students) (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015) to allow a deeper insight into the ways in which open schooling educational actions influence students' interest in science and career awareness. The participants were divided into four classrooms attending an urban secondary school in Cyprus taught by two science teachers.

Framed within the 'Design-Based Research' (DBR) paradigm (Brown, 1992) the research is design-driven and intervention-focused. The setting of this study interplays within the classroom environment and the wider community in collaboration between researchers, teachers, STEM experts, and civil society organisations. The study unfolded based on the open-schooling TLS framework focusing on the socio-scientific issue of Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) in the teaching unit of 'Microbes and Disease' (Drymiotou & Constantinou, 2023). AMR is a critical issue around the globe affecting our health and putting our lives at risk. Overwhelming evidence shows that increased use of antibiotics, over-prescription, and overconsumption are leading to an increase in resistant bugs (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control [ECDC], 2022). Cyprus where this study takes place ranks amongst the EU/EEA countries with the highest consumption of antibiotics (ECDC, 2022). A vital step towards tackling this issue is education and informed action. Table 1 describes the ongoing TLS that was co-developed between researchers, teachers and biology experts. The enactment consisted of 20 sessions (1 session= 50') excluding after-school hours.

Table 1. Open schooling Teaching and Learning Sequence around AMR

Open Schooling TLS Phases	No of Sessions (S) and Short Description
1. Identification and Exploration of the SSI of relevance to the local community (5 sessions)	S1. Introduction to AMR building on previous knowledge. S2-3. Students explore the issue of AMR in stakeholder groups (i.e., pharmacists, policymakers, farmers, patients, academia, media) using authentic media and evaluate the information using the TAAP test (Time-Authority-Accuracy-Purpose test, adjusted version of CRAAP test). S4: Introduction to argumentation: identifying and formulating arguments. S5: Debate within the stakeholder groups on the topic 'We should ban the use of antibiotics for the treatment of flu. Do you agree or disagree?'
2. Engagement in the Open Schooling Science-learning project (10 sessions)	S6. Experts visit the school, discuss the importance of AMR, and share an overview of the visit to the premises the day after. S7-9. Students visit experts' premises and engage in authentic activities and scientific practices. S10. Experts visit the school to summarise the key messages from S7 and show photos of bacteria culture collected from students' hands. S11. Presentation of students' mission to start an awareness-raising campaign for AMR consisting of different projects.

	S12-15: Development of the Open Schooling projects.
3. Acting as knowledge multipliers (5 sessions)	S16. Presentation of the projects to the local science fair (sCYence fair). S18-20. Presentation of the projects to the awareness-raising campaign at the central square of the capital.

Data Collection

To investigate whether open schooling influences students' interest and career awareness, a combination of quantitative and qualitative data was collected. Quantitative data were collected using an adjusted version of the Scenario Evaluation with Relevance and Interest (SERI) (Kang et al., 2021). Qualitative data were retrieved from interviews with the students on the added value of their experience with the open schooling TLS, in terms of enhancing their interest in science and raising awareness about science careers. Interviews with the students were conducted after S11 and Phase 3.

The adjusted version of the SERI questionnaire consists of 16 items related to interest (8 items), self-efficacy (4 items) and career awareness (4 items) on a 4-point Likert scale (from *strongly disagree* to *strongly agree*; *not well informed* to *very well informed*). For this pilot study, we considered the items related to interest and career awareness as displayed in Image 1 below. The questionnaire was administered before the beginning of Phase 1 and after Phase 3.

SCIENCE INTEREST (8 items)				
How strongly do you agree?	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
I really like science.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Doing science is one of my favourite activities.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I enjoy science courses.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I would like to find out much more about some of the things we deal with in our science class.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Science is relevant to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Science is important for helping us to understand the natural world.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Science is valuable to society.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I find that science helps me to understand the things around me.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
SCIENCE CAREER AWARENESS (4 items)				
How informed are you?	Not well informed	Somewhat informed	Informed	Very well informed
Science-related careers that are available in the job market.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Where to find information about science-related careers.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The steps students need to take if they want a science-related career.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Employers or companies that hire people to work in science-related careers.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Image 1. Snapshot of the questionnaire given as a pre - and post-test.

Qualitative data were also collected through ten focus group interviews (8-10') with 20 students (4 in each group) after S11 and Phase 3, and two science teachers (in total, twelve interviews). The interviews were semi-structured in both cases and focused on providing insights into the ways in which the open schooling works (or not) towards enhancing interest in science and career awareness (e.g., successful activities/methods, obstacles, suggestions for improvement). The students were selected based on their scores on the questionnaire including a diversity of levels concerning interest in science respecting gender diversity as well (11 female and 9 male students).

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analysed using a pre- and post- data comparison to provide an overall indication of students' interest in science and awareness about science careers using the SPSS software (version 29). Data were skewed for one of the two variables, and a Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test was run to find the difference between the two measurements also comparing the median value of the changes in students' answers before and after the intervention for each of the studied variables. Qualitative data from the interviews with the students were analysed using open coding with respect to the features that seemed to enhance interest and career awareness.

Results and Discussion

Findings from the quantitative analysis

Overall, the findings from the quantitative analysis indicated that the intervention had a positive impact on both students' interest in science as well as their awareness about science-related careers. According to the results (Table 2), the post-test scores for students' interest in science were statistically significantly higher than the pre-test scores, $Z = -3.58$, $p < .001$. Similarly, the post-test scores for students' career awareness in science were statistically significantly higher than the pre-test scores, $Z = -3.25$, $p = .001$.

Table 2. Comparing students' science interest and career awareness before and after the intervention using the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test results.

Variable (post-pre)	Ranks	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	p
Interest	Neg.	14	33.43	468.00	-3.58	<.001
	Pos.	48	30.94	1485.00		
	Ties	12				
Career awareness	Neg.	19	29.32	557.00	-3.25	.001
	Pos.	45	33.84	1523.00		
	Ties	10				

According to further analysis in each of the question items it was found that students' post score for question item 2 'Doing science is one of my favourite activities' had a statistically significant difference than the pre-test score compared to the other items, $Z = -6.96$, $p < .001$. Likewise, considering the career awareness-related items, statistically significant differences were found in 3 out of the 4 question-items (i.e., 'Science-related careers that are available in the job market'; 'The steps students need to take if they want a science-related science'; and 'Employers or companies that hire people to work in science-related careers'). In these three question-items, the students' post-test scores were statistically significantly higher than the pre-test scores, $Z = -2.12$, $p < .05$, $Z = -3.46$, $p < .001$, and $Z = -3.11$, $p < .002$, respectively.

Findings from the qualitative analysis

The qualitative analysis using open coding with respect to the features that seemed to promote interest in science facilitated the emergence of three categories with their frequencies as shown on Table 3 below. Specifically, the categories shed light on what the students found more interesting/liked more which provides further insights on the ways in which the open schooling mechanism influenced their interest in science. The frequencies indicate the number of times the students mentioned these features in each category and code.

Table 3. Features that enhance students' interest in science according to the analysis of the interviews with students (n=20).

Features	Frequencies
Novelty	26
Open schooling events	10
Interaction with experts in an authentic environment	9
Scientific practices	7
Knowledge	16
Sharing knowledge	9
Learning/knowledge gained (AMR and careers)	7
Social relatedness	5
Working in groups	3
Social interaction	2

As can be derived from Table 3, the novelty aspect (n=26) was found to have influenced students' interest significantly. Students' participation in the open schooling events was perceived as remarkably interesting for the students (n=10) as well as their interaction with the experts (n=9)

and the engagement with the scientific practices (n=7). The excerpts on Table 4 below from the interviews with the students are indicative of the supporting evidence.

Table 4. Excerpts from interviews with the students indicate novelty as a feature that enhances interest in science.

Category	Code	Excerpts from the interviews with the students
Novelty	Open schooling events	The sCYence fair was a lot of fun. The acting was fun. We had a lot of people to find out about this problem. I was going around asking people if they would like to come and I think there was only one person that knew what AMR was, everyone else said they didn't, so it was nice to get them to know what it is. (8RSR)
	Interaction with experts	I loved the trip to the biobank. It wasn't like every trip to the museum, boring. We had activities, it was interesting. We experienced some things we can't forget. (8PGMi) It was the first time that I interacted with scientists in their workplace. Apart from AMR, I learn about another study they do with public testing. Some people there were collecting urine samples to test for different things, there was a lab manager and some other people who worked to analyse different samples with microscopes. (8PKI)
	Scientific practices	I liked it because it felt more like we were really doing something instead of just learning. For example, we did research on the groups that we were representing and worked on real case studies, we had to look on proper medical websites. It felt like were not just kids in the class. It felt like we were actually doing a job. (8PKI)

The analysis of the qualitative data provides insights that support the results from the statistical analysis indicating the statistically significant difference with respect to question-item 2 'Doing science is one of my favourite activities'. It was evident that the open schooling events (i.e., science fair, awareness-raising campaign), the interaction with experts in an authentic environment as well as the engagement in scientific practices using authentic media and research equipment were perceived as an innovative feature in the school science. What becomes of interest here is that students' interactions with the experts provided the opportunity to enhance their understandings of science careers, how scientists work, what it takes to become a scientist and the skills required. This finding is consistent with the results of the statistical analysis indicating that students reported feeling 'very well informed' about the necessary steps for pursuing a science-related career and the available opportunities in such fields.

Additional data from the interviews with the teachers support that these activities were interesting and useful to understand the science can offer for all the students regardless of their academic performance. This view is exemplified in the excerpt that follows from the interview with one of teachers:

Certainly, the brightest students got a lot out of this. They put a lot in, and they put a lot out of it. The less able also enjoyed it and they were able to find a path through the project and the exercises and that it is more self-motivative for them. It's been quite a revelation how excited, interested and engaged the students have been in this, even students I wasn't expecting to be engaged. They obviously engaged in different degrees, but I think across the board the level of interest in the subject contents and the materials have been really very high. I would think that they got more engaged in science, more understanding of what science can offer and how broad science is, and they are more motivated in learning the subject. [...] I really liked the fact that we tried to introduce different experts to them, but I think because there were so many students, we couldn't really introduce the experts to them on a more personal level. I think it needs to be a little bit more concise, but they are way more aware about what scientists do than they were aware before because they got to see how they work in the lab, that was good for them. (Teacher A)

The words above illustrate that the students received career-related information, but more thorough planning needs to be considered for the main study by promoting a more personal (one

on one) interaction with the experts.

Furthermore, responses placed under the category of knowledge (16) indicate that the students were more interested in sharing knowledge about AMR (9) than in learning new information with respect to the topic and the relevant careers (7). Finally, the less common category was social relatedness with students reporting being interested in group work (3) and in social interaction (2). Excerpts from the interviews with the students are some representative examples:

Table 5. Excerpts from interviews with the students indicate knowledge and social relatedness as features that enhance interest in science.

Category	Code	Excerpts from the interviews with the students
Knowledge	Learning/ knowledge gained	I liked learning lots of different things about antibiotics and resistance. The whole process was really fun and interesting. I loved every part of it. (8RSR)
	Sharing knowledge	I really felt that we were starting to show people what the problem was, and it was interesting to see that they did not really know anything and how they were interested in this. (8PKI)
	Raising awareness about AMR	Every single person I asked whether they knew about AMR, none knew, and it was good teaching them about this problem and ways to stop it. (8RSR)
Social relatedness	Working in groups	I liked all the projects we had to do because it was fun teaming up with other people. (8RSR)
	Social interaction	I liked the sCYence fair most because we displayed our posters and spread awareness about the issue while having fun and being able to do something interactive with the people. (8UDT)

Indicatively, the students were more interested in the novel activities than in learning and sharing knowledge. This implies that the students were engaged in scientific practices they were not familiar with in school science (e.g., argumentation and critical thinking tasks) and probably they were not feeling confident enough to reflect on the new knowledge and share it with other people.

Conclusions

The findings of this study suggest that open-schooling educational initiatives, as compared to traditional school science, contribute to students' perception of real science as more enjoyable, interesting, relevant, and informative with respect to careers, especially when they promote novelty, knowledge, and social connections. This pilot study showcased specific features that enhanced students' interest in science and career awareness, aligning with prior research (Drymiotou et al., 2021b) as follows: (a) organising open schooling events in the wider community; (b) interacting with experts in an authentic environment; (c) engaging in scientific practices; (d) promoting and sharing knowledge in general and specifically with respect to societal challenges; (e) promoting group work and social interaction.

Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that this pilot study has not investigated the role of the teacher in this intervention as well as the preparedness of the experts to act as science communicators. Hence, we recommend exploring these two factors in the main study as they might influence the findings.

In conclusion, these findings hold important implications as they offer insights to: (a) inform the design of open-schooling teaching and learning activities; (b) further develop the open-schooling TLS framework, and (c) provide practical recommendations for curriculum design and classroom practices to enrich the curricula and pedagogical approaches in school science toward enhancing students' interest in science and awareness about science careers. One can argue that these activities opened students a window to real science providing connections between theory and practice.

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